

Energy Management Strategies for Optimal Operation of a Dual Chemistry Hybrid Battery System on a Modular Power Barge

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Abstract—This paper presents an energy management strategy developed for a floating power barge that integrates two containerized battery technologies with distinct chemical structures and compliance levels, maritime-grade lithium-ion batteries and non-maritime VRFBs (vanadium redox flow batteries), forming a hybrid energy storage system. This combination enables both high-power and long-duration operation, aiming to supply zero-emission electricity to moored and anchored vessels. Unlike most of the maritime battery applications that rely almost exclusively on Li-ion batteries, this project leverages the complementary characteristics of both battery types through a custom-developed EMS (Energy Management System). The proposed EMS defines two primary operational modes, charging and discharging, and dynamically adjusts its strategy based on predicted barge mission scenarios. During charging, the EMS considers the duration of shore power availability and the expected future operation of the barge (e.g., supplying hotel loads to a specific ship type such as a tanker). By incorporating these mission parameters, the EMS allocates charging power between the Li-ion and VRFB subsystems according to their distinct energy and power characteristics, ensuring that each battery is prepared to perform optimally during the upcoming task. A high-level simulation environment incorporating battery models, power electronics, and maritime load profiles is used to validate the EMS. Simulation results demonstrate effective hybrid utilization, improved SoC (State of Charge) stability, and reduced stress on lithium-ion units under dynamic load conditions.

Keywords—Energy Management System, Hybrid Energy Storage Systems, Maritime Decarbonisation, Floating Power Barge, Vanadium Redox Flow Battery, Lithium Ion Battery.

I. INTRODUCTION

Maritime transport accounts for approximately 1,076 million tons of CO₂ emissions annually, driven by the consumption of nearly 300 million tons of fossil-based marine

fuels [1]. While regulations have led to a gradual shift from HFO (heavy fuel oil) to cleaner MDO (marine diesel oils) [2], the industry's carbon footprint remains substantial and is projected to grow significantly under a business-as-usual scenario. In response, regulatory frameworks such as the IMO's (International Maritime Organization) Greenhouse Gas Strategy and the EU's "Fit for 55" package are accelerating the push toward maritime decarbonization through stricter efficiency measures and carbon pricing mechanisms. One particularly effective mitigation strategy is the provision of onshore electrical power, commonly known as cold ironing or SSE (Shore-Side Electricity), which eliminates shipboard emissions while vessels are berthed. However, ships at anchorage, often idle for extended periods, still rely heavily on auxiliary diesel generators, contributing significantly to local and global emissions. This presents a critical need for flexible, mobile, and zero-emission offshore power supply solutions.

Lithium-ion batteries remain the dominant technology in maritime energy storage applications due to their high energy density (95–500 Wh/L) [3] and fast response. In addition, the dramatic cost reduction of about 85 % over the past decade contributed to their rapidly decreasing upfront costs [4]. However, their sensitivity to deep discharges, limited cycle life (1,000–10,000 cycles), and degraded operation at elevated temperatures [5] restrict their suitability for long-duration and high-cycling maritime missions. In contrast, VRFBs offer lower energy density (10–70 Wh/L), but provide excellent scalability, tolerance to deep discharge, and very high cycle life (10,000–15,000 cycles) with minimal degradation [6], VRFBs also allow independent scaling of power and energy and have a projected lower levelized cost of storage over long service lifetimes [7], especially in stationary or semi-mobile use cases like offshore barges. These complementary characteristics make the combination of Li-ion and VRFBs a promising hybrid solution. However, chemically heterogeneous hybrid systems remain largely untested in maritime applications, and

there is a lack of standardized energy management strategies to coordinate such diverse battery types aboard floating platforms. This study examines a modular floating power barge designed to deliver clean and flexible electrical energy in a variety of maritime scenarios where conventional OPS (Onshore Power Supply) infrastructure may be unavailable, insufficient, or economically infeasible. These scenarios include supporting berthed vessels in underdeveloped or grid-constrained ports, supplying power to ships at anchorage, enabling cold ironing in small islands or remote coastal regions, and providing temporary reinforcement to local grid infrastructure during emergencies.

The barge incorporates a hybrid energy storage system that combines lithium-ion batteries and VRFBs, leveraging the high-power density and dynamic response characteristics of lithium-ion technology alongside the deep cycling capability and extended service life of VRFBs. This chemically diverse configuration is integrated into a containerized and mobile platform, enabling scalable and mission-adaptable offshore energy delivery. The energy management strategy presented in this paper is specifically developed for heterogeneous systems and is tailored to coordinate battery operation based on mission profiles and shore connection constraints. The control algorithm considers inputs such as the available charging duration and the predicted parameters of the barge's upcoming operational task, including vessel type and estimated hotel load. Based on these inputs, the strategy allocates charging power across the two battery systems within the available time window and regulates the discharge behavior in accordance with optimal power levels, with the aim of maximizing efficiency and extending the lifetime of both storage systems.

II. POWER BARGE ELECTRICAL SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

A. Vanadium Redox Flow Battery System

VRFB, like all electrochemical energy storage systems, operates based on reversible redox reactions, also known as oxidation–reduction reactions. Unlike conventional batteries, where active materials are immobilized within the cell structure, VRFBs store the electroactive species externally in separate electrolyte tanks. These electrolytes are continuously circulated through electrochemical cells, where redox reactions occur, enabling charge and discharge processes depending on the flow direction. VRFBs utilize vanadium ions in different oxidation states on both positive and negative electrodes, which eliminates cross-contamination risks and enhances cycle stability [8].

The charge storage mechanism is based on the following redox reactions:

Positive electrode reaction,

Negative electrode reaction,

During charging, VO^{2+} is oxidized to VO_2^+ at the positive electrode, while V^{3+} is reduced to V^{2+} at the negative electrode; these reactions reverse during discharge. This symmetric use of vanadium in both half-cells ensures chemical compatibility and avoids the degradation associated with cross-mixing of electrolytes.

Due to their reliance on liquid electrolytes, VRFBs typically exhibit relatively low volumetric energy densities, commonly in the range of 25–35 Wh/L [9]. However, a significant advantage of VRFB technology is the decoupling of power and energy capacities. Power output depends primarily on the electrochemical cell stack size (electrode surface area and number of cells), while energy capacity is governed by the volume and concentration of vanadium electrolyte stored externally. This design flexibility enables scalable configurations tailored to application-specific requirements. In the modular power barge system analyzed in this study, the VRFB system is designed with two power blocks connected in series. Each block operates over a nominal voltage range of 50–86 V DC across the full SoC range (0–100%), yielding a combined system voltage from 100 to 172 V DC. Each block provides 50 kW rated power, resulting in a total output of 100 kW and an energy capacity of 400 kWh.

Thermal management, electrolyte flow rate control, and SoC monitoring are critical for maintaining system efficiency and durability. Furthermore, VRFBs offer excellent cycle life, in the range of 15,000–20,000 full cycles [10], with minimal capacity degradation due to their reversible electrochemistry and stable electrolyte solutions. The VRFB technology presents an option for large-scale marine energy storage, combining modularity, long cycle life, and operational flexibility, making it well-suited to applications such as power barges requiring scalable, reliable, and sustainable energy storage solutions.

B. Lithium-Ion Battery System

Lithium-ion battery systems are widely adopted in marine energy storage applications due to their high gravimetric and volumetric energy density, rapid dynamic response, and advanced system integration maturity. The specific chemistry employed in this system is NMC (lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxide), which offers a balanced profile between energy capacity, thermal stability, and cycle life. NMC cathodes operate within a typical voltage window of 3.6–3.7 V per cell, depending on the SoC and operating temperature, and are characterized by relatively low internal resistance and favorable coulombic efficiency across a range of C-rates [11].

The evaluated BESS (Battery Energy Storage System) delivers a nominal energy capacity of 1045.4 kWh, with a usable capacity of 836.4 kWh, reflecting DoD (Depth of Discharge) constraints optimized for performance stability and degradation minimization. Under standard marine operation (0.5C charge/discharge rate within a 10–90% SoC band), the system exhibits a roundtrip efficiency exceeding 90%. The system enables bidirectional power flow of up to 500 kW and operates within a DC voltage range of 818.4 V to 1082.4 V, corresponding to the cumulative voltage of series-connected cells across each module.

Fig. 1. Configuration of the Dual Chemistry BESS

Structurally, the BESS comprises nine independent packs, each containing 20 modules connected in series. This modular topology enhances redundancy, facilitates thermal and fault management, and supports scalable system design. The BMS (Battery Management System) governs cell-level balancing, voltage and current protection, and thermal oversight, ensuring operational safety across all load profiles and environmental conditions.

C. Inverter Control Strategy and Synchronization Architecture for Multi-Chemistry Battery Integration

This section presents the control system design and synchronization methodology applied to GFMI (Grid-forming Inverter) operating in parallel within a microgrid environment. The inverter and controller architecture are specifically tailored to support dual battery chemistries introduced in earlier sections. The control approach leverages decentralized droop-based mechanisms, enabling autonomous power sharing and seamless parallel operation without relying on communication links [12].

1) Droop Control Principle for Power Sharing

Droop control enables the independent regulation of active (P) and reactive (Q) power among parallel-operating GFMI. This technique eliminates the need for direct communication

between units, thus enhancing system reliability and scalability. The method relies on local measurements and introduces a proportional change in inverter voltage magnitude and frequency in response to real-time power variations [13].

The fundamental droop equations governing the active and reactive power adjustments are given by:

$$\omega^* = \omega_0 - mP \quad (3)$$

$$V^* = V_0 - nQ \quad (4)$$

In this context, ω^* and V^* represent the frequency and voltage setpoints, respectively, while ω_0 and V_0 denote the nominal frequency and voltage values. The parameters m and n correspond to the droop coefficients, which are defined based on the desired power-sharing behavior and dynamic characteristics of the system.

$$m = \frac{\Delta\omega}{P_{max}} \quad (5)$$

$$n = \frac{\Delta V}{Q_{max}} \quad (6)$$

These coefficients are selected based on system tolerances for maximum frequency deviation $\Delta\omega$ and voltage variation ΔV , aligned with international standards for grid stability and RoCoF (Rate of Change of Frequency) constraints.

2) Power Flow Model and Simplified Control Equations

Assuming an inductive line impedance $Z_l = R_l + jX_l$ between a GFMI and the PCC (Point of Common Coupling), active and reactive power can be expressed as:

$$P = \frac{V_1}{R_1^2 + X_1^2} \cdot [R_1(V_1 - V_2 \cos \delta) + X_1 V_2 \sin \delta] \quad (7)$$

$$Q = \frac{V_1}{R_1^2 + X_1^2} \cdot [X_1(V_1 - V_2 \cos \delta) + R_1 V_2 \sin \delta] \quad (8)$$

Under the assumptions $\delta \ll 1$, $\sin \delta \approx \delta$, $\cos \delta \approx 1$, and $R_l \ll X_l$, simplified forms become:

$$P \approx \frac{V_1 V_2}{X_1} \delta, \quad Q \approx \frac{V_1(V_1 - V_2)}{X_1} \quad (9)$$

These expressions illustrate that:

- Active power flow is primarily a function of phase angle δ ,
- Reactive power flow depends on voltage magnitude differences.

This decoupling underpins the feasibility of independent droop-based regulation for P and Q .

3) Pre-Synchronization of GFM Inverters

Before physically connecting an additional GFMI in parallel, a three-step pre-synchronization procedure is necessary to align voltage amplitude, frequency, and phase with the existing PCC waveform. This prevents circulating currents and voltage instability [14].

The inverter under synchronization be GFMI₁, and the PCC be regulated by GFMI₀. The controller ensures:

1. Voltage Magnitude Matching
2. Frequency Alignment via Droop + PLL (Phase Locked Loop)
3. Phase Tracking using DSOGI-PLL (Dual Second Order Generalized Integrator PLL)

The voltage synchronization loop is executed in the stationary reference frame ($\alpha\beta 0$), using a Clarke transformation:

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_\alpha \\ V_\beta \\ V_0 \end{bmatrix} = \omega_{ref} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1/2 & -1/2 \\ 0 & \sqrt{3}/2 & -\sqrt{3}/2 \\ 1/2 & 1/2 & 1/2 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} V_a \\ V_b \\ V_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The frequency and phase synchronization loops are handled using DSOGI-PLL, which ensures robust estimation of the phase angle θ_{pcc} under distorted grid conditions. Synchronization is deemed complete when:

$$|V^* - V_{pcc}| < \epsilon_V \quad (11)$$

$$|\omega^* - \omega_{pcc}| < \epsilon_\omega \quad (12)$$

$$|\theta^* - \theta_{pcc}| < \epsilon_\theta \quad (13)$$

Where ϵ_V , ϵ_ω , ϵ_θ , are predefined tolerances. Once synchronization completes, the inverter is safely connected, and corrective terms $\Delta\omega$, $\Delta\theta$ are frozen.

4) Active Power Sharing and Dynamic Effects

In steady-state operation, droop-controlled GFMI_s adjust output power based on their assigned coefficients:

$$\omega_0^* = \omega_{nom} - m_0 P_0 \quad (14)$$

$$\omega_1^* = \omega_{nom} - m_1 P_1 \quad (15)$$

Equating frequency references in steady-state ($\omega_0^* = \omega_1^*$) leads to:

$$\frac{P_0}{P_1} = \frac{m_1}{m_0} \quad (16)$$

This relation governs power sharing proportionality. During transients (load steps), droop mismatches cause frequency and phase oscillations between GFMI_s, resulting in power swings. To mitigate this, a derivative term can be added to the droop law, forming a proportional-derivative droop scheme (P-D droop), enhancing damping:

$$\omega^* = \omega_0 - mP - d \frac{dP}{dt} \quad (16)$$

5) Control Architecture and Implementation

The unified inverter control architecture employed for both battery chemistries is illustrated in Fig. 11. This configuration adopts a layered control strategy comprising inner voltage and current regulation loops that ensure stable and responsive output across diverse operating conditions. Encapsulating these, outer droop control loops govern active and reactive power sharing via P- ω and Q-V mechanisms, enabling decentralized coordination among multiple GFMI_s. To support seamless grid integration, the system includes pre-synchronization PI (Proportional-Integral) controllers that align voltage amplitude, phase, and frequency prior to interconnection. For precise phase tracking under distorted or unbalanced network conditions, a DSOGI-PLL is utilized, providing enhanced robustness in dynamic maritime environments.

The controller design is adapted to the electrochemical characteristics of each battery type. GFMI_s interfaced with lithium-ion batteries exhibit fast dynamic response and tight voltage regulation due to the high-power density and rapid

electrochemical kinetics of Li-ion systems. Conversely, GFMI connected to VRFBs operate with slower dynamic profiles and broader allowable SoC ranges, reflecting the thermal and hydraulic limitations intrinsic to flow battery technologies. These control adaptations ensure optimal performance and system stability under hybrid energy storage operations.

III. ENERGY MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

The integration of lithium-ion and VRFBs into a single power platform introduces operational complexity due to their differing electrochemical characteristics, efficiency profiles, and degradation behaviors. Notably, VRFBs support a deep discharge down to 0% SoC without significant performance loss, making them suitable for long-duration, constant power delivery. In contrast, lithium-ion batteries are more sensitive to deep cycling and are therefore operated within restricted SoC boundaries to maximize lifetime. The EMS designed for the floating power barge draws conceptual parallels from hybrid diesel-generator systems, where batteries are commonly used to ensure generator sets operate closer to their optimal efficiency points. For instance, during low-load conditions, batteries can absorb excess capacity to avoid running generator sets at inefficient partial loads; conversely, batteries may supply temporary load peaks to avoid starting additional generator sets operating at suboptimal levels [15]. Extending this principle to chemically heterogeneous battery systems, the EMS strategically coordinates VRFBs and lithium-ion batteries to match the temporal profile of power demand in the operational scenarios of the barge. VRFBs are prioritized for supplying predictable base loads due to their robustness and deep cycling capability, while lithium-ion batteries are reserved for fast-response to transient peak loads. The EMS executes this strategy by considering shore connection availability, forecasted mission requirements, battery SoC, and system constraints. It is implemented through a rule-based control framework and validated in a high-level simulation environment representing the operational scenarios of the barge.

A. Objectives and Design Principles

The primary objective of the developed EMS is to coordinate the hybrid battery system in a way that ensures efficient energy utilization, chemistry-aware control, and mission-oriented flexibility. A key design principle is the optimized use of limited charging windows during shore connection. To achieve this, the EMS takes as input the predicted available charging time and the upcoming operational scenario of the barge, such as the type of vessel it will support and the expected hotel load. This allows EMS to distribute the charging power between the lithium-ion and VRFBs in an optimal way based on their roles in the next mission. In this strategy, VRFBs, capable of deep discharge and robust cycling, are typically allocated for steady base loads, while Li-ion batteries, with their higher power density but more limited depth-of-discharge tolerance, are reserved for transient peak demands. The EMS dynamically adjusts this coordination to ensure that each battery type operates within its most favorable performance zone, enhancing overall system efficiency and extending battery lifetimes.

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the proposed EMS

B. Operational Modes

The EMS implemented for the power barge operates through two principal operational phases: charging and discharging, each comprising three internal control sub-modes. These modes are selected based on system state, mission requirements, and real-time or forecasted operational parameters. The decision-making process governing the discharging state is illustrated in Figure 2, which outlines the high-level flow of EMS operations.

In charging mode, the EMS selects one of three strategies depending on the barge's forecasted mission and time availability at shore connection:

- **Li-ion Priority Charging:** All available charging power is directed toward lithium-ion batteries until a target SoC threshold is reached, after which charging may cease or shift to the other battery.
- **VRFB Priority Charging:** Charging is directed primarily to VRFBs, exploiting their ability to accept deep charge cycles.
- **Mission-Based Optimal Charging:** This mode evaluates the time available for charging and the predicted load profile of the upcoming mission to proportionally distribute charging power between both battery types. This ensures that both batteries are charged in a way that optimally supports the next operational profile.

Similarly, in discharging mode, the EMS operates under one of the following sub-modes:

- **Li-ion Priority Discharge:** The lithium-ion battery bank is discharged first down to a predefined low SoC limit. Once this threshold is reached, the EMS shifts load support to the VRFBs.
- **VRFB Priority Discharge:** The EMS prioritizes VRFBs for base load support due to their deep discharge tolerance, shifting to Li-ion batteries only when additional power is required.
- **Optimal Coordinated Discharge:** This mode manages both batteries concurrently, dispatching VRFBs for sustained base load coverage, and leveraging Li-ion batteries to respond to peak load events or rapid

power fluctuations. This coordinated strategy enhances both operational efficiency and battery lifetime.

IV. BARGE POWER SYSTEM SIMULATION

In this section, the electrical model of the dual-chemistry hybrid power barge system was developed. The complete system is modeled in MATLAB®/Simulink and illustrated in Figure 3. The model consists of two battery drives, an energy management system, and load and measurement sections. Energy management and power control strategies were tested on the model developed in the simulation environment, and the dynamic responses of the control systems were analyzed. Scenario-based simulations were conducted using load profiles representative of real-world operating conditions, and the functionality of the various operational modes was validated through the resulting simulation data.

A. System Modeling

The model comprises multiple interconnected subsystems, including Li-ion and VRFB battery drive units operating under droop control and include their respective battery model, VSI (Voltage Source Inverter) with voltage and current control loops, isolation transformers, and circuit breakers. A dedicated EMS is implemented to regulate power sharing between battery drives. Additionally, load and measurement sections are integrated to evaluate the performance of the energy management system under predefined load profiles and to assess the overall system through simulation.

1) Battery Models

The models for the Li-ion and VRFB batteries are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, respectively. The battery models include the equivalent resistance of the respective battery system to analyze the battery behavior in steady-state conditions.

The DC-bus voltage of each VSI is assumed to be constant, and the current drawn by each battery is scaled according to the ratio between DC-bus voltage and the battery OCV (Open-Circuit Voltage).

Fig. 3. Dual Chemistry Hybrid Battery Simulation Model.

Fig. 4. VRFB Battery Model

Fig. 5. Lithium-ion Battery Model

The SoC of the battery is updated using the Coulomb Counting Method and the OCV of each battery is calculated using distinct look-up tables for charge and discharge cases.

The SoC versus OCV characteristics for the VRFB and Li-ion batteries are presented in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively. For both battery types, the reference curves were scaled appropriately to reflect the configurations used in the simulation model: the VRFB curve was adapted from a 50-kW module, while the Li-ion curve was derived from a single cell and scaled according to its series and parallel arrangement within the battery drive. The battery parameters used in the simulation model are given in Table I.

Fig. 6. SOC-OCV Curve of the 50-kW VRFB Battery Block

TABLE I. BATTERY PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Unit
VRFB - Nominal Power	100	kW
VRFB – Energy Capacity	400	kWh
VRFB - Equivalent Resistance	14	mΩ
Li-ion – Nominal Power	500	kW
Li-ion – Energy Capacity	1015	kWh
Li-ion – Nominal Voltage	880	V
Li-ion – Max Capacity	1152	Ah
Li-ion – Nominal Discharge Current	650	A
Li-ion – Equivalent Resistance	10.3	mΩ

2) Power Electronics Models

VSI s are employed within the battery drive systems to interface the batteries with the AC grid, incorporating LCL filters at the output to increase the power quality and stability of the system. Each VSI is constituted by a two-layer control structure, internal voltage and current controllers with a faster response, and an external droop controller with a slower response. The simulation parameters, along with the detailed specifications of the VSIs and LCL filters, are provided in Table II.

Galvanic isolation is a requirement in battery applications with different chemistries to ensure safe operation, especially in high-power applications. Hence, the VSIs are connected to the AC grid via isolation transformers. Isolation transformers are also used in maritime applications to help suppress common-mode noise and provide voltage matching between the inverter output and the grid.

The circuit breakers are configured to disconnect the battery drive units from the system in the event of a load connection to the AC busbar that exceeds the maximum power rating of the system. This protective mechanism ensures safe operation by preventing overloading conditions and potential system instability.

Fig. 7. SOC-OCV Curve of the Li-ion Battery Cell

TABLE II. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value	Unit
VSI Power	500	kVA
VSI Switching Frequency	7.5	kHz
LCL Filter Inductance - 1	50	μH
LCL Filter Inductance - 2	50	μH
LCL Filter Capacitance	1000	μF
DC-Link Voltage	1000	V

3) Energy Management System

The EMS block previously described in Figure 2 receives the load demand and the SoC of each battery as inputs to determine the appropriate power sharing among the inverters based on the active operating mode. Power references defined by the EMS are translated into droop coefficients, which modulate the frequency of each converter to achieve the desired power distribution.

B. Simulation Scenarios

In this section, the EMS is tested under a load profile and the transitions between modes are analyzed according to the load demand and SoC of the batteries. The load sharing capability of the proposed EMS is presented in two distinct cases.

1) Case - I

In Case -I, the transition from Optimal Coordinated Discharge to Li-ion Priority Discharge is tested when the SoC of VRFB batteries falls below the specified limit. The simulation starts with a constant load connected to the system, where the EMS performed load sharing between the two battery systems by controlling the droop coefficients for the battery drives according to the active power input from the load. The ratio of the power share between the batteries is updated when an additional load is added between $t = 1$ s and $t = 3$ s. At $t = 5$ s, the SoC of the VRFB battery falls under the specified limit, and the VRFB battery drive is disconnected from the rest of the system by BPMS. From this point onward, the load demand is provided by the Li-ion battery system until the end of the simulation.

Fig. 8. Power vs Time Graph for Case - I

Fig. 9. Frequency vs Time Graph for Case - I

Fig. 10. SoC vs Time Graph for Case - I

The loads connected to the system and the load sharing between two VSIs for Case - I is presented in Figure 8. The frequency response of VSIs to load sharing is shown in Figure 9. The change in SoC of the batteries is given in Figure 10.

2) Case - II

This case is structured similar to Case - I, where the transition from Optimal Coordinated Discharge to VRFB Priority Discharge is tested when the SoC of Li-ion batteries falls below the specified limit. The system operates in the same manner from $t = 0$ to $t = 5$ s. At $t = 5$ s, the SoC of the Li-ion battery falls under the specified limit, and the Li-ion battery drive is disconnected from the rest of the system by EMS. From this point onward, the load demand is provided by the VRFB battery system until the end of the simulation.

Fig. 11. Power vs Time Graph for Case - II

Fig. 12. Frequency vs Time Graph for Case - II

Fig. 13. SoC vs Time Graph for Case - II

The loads connected to the system and the load sharing between two VSIs for Case - II is presented in Figure 11. The frequency response of the VSIs to load sharing is shown in Figure 12. The change in SoC of batteries is given in Figure 13.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, an energy management strategy for a modular floating power barge equipped with a hybrid battery system consisting of lithium-ion and vanadium redox flow batteries was developed. A rule-based methodology was designed to coordinate the charging and discharging of the two battery chemistries in accordance with operation profiles and shore connection constraints. The paper detailed the power barge's electrical system architecture, analyzed the characteristics of both battery chemistries, and presented the inverter control and synchronization strategy, including the droop-controlled inverter principles and synchronization requirements. The implemented energy management system was validated through a comprehensive simulation model incorporating battery dynamics, power electronics, and maritime load profiles. Simulation results demonstrated effective coordination between the hybrid battery systems under discharging conditions, verifying the EMS's capability to optimize power delivery while respecting system constraints. The modular hybrid architecture provides a flexible power platform suitable for various maritime applications such as supplying berthed vessels in grid-constrained ports, powering anchored ships, and reinforcing local grids during emergencies. The proposed EMS is not limited to barge applications; it can also be effectively adapted to shipboard systems that incorporate hybrid battery configurations. Its modular structure and flexibility in handling multiple storage technologies make it suitable for a wider range of marine applications beyond the scope of barge-specific use cases. Future work will focus on extending the current rule-based approach by applying model predictive control techniques to enhance decision-making capabilities, improve battery lifetime management, and integrate cost and emission optimization objectives.

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